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MUNDARIJA

Turizmning zamonaviy yo'nalishlarini rivojlantirish xususiyatlari	17
Xolmurzayev Sobir Nazarovich	
Tashqi iqtisodiy sharoitlar o'zgarishining o'zbekistondagi narxlar darajasiga ta'siri.....	23
Duskobilov Umidjon Sharofiddinovich	
The main influencers of the quality assurance in tertiary education	29
Shakirova Dilfuza Tulkunovna	
Xizmat ko'rsatish korxonalarida ishchi-xodimlarni boshqarish tizimini optimallashtirish.....	35
Sultonov Sanjar Jaxongir o'g'li	
O'zbekistonda tungi iqtisodiyotni rivojlantirishning ahamiyati va dolzarbligi.....	41
Normamatov Ne'mat Daminovich	
Ta'lim menejerining professionalligini shakllantirishning o'ziga xos xususiyatlari	45
Abdullayev O'tkir Sadullayevich	
Ekologik buxgalteriya hisobining uslubiy jihatlari.....	57
Hatidje Nasirova	
Tadbirkorlikni davlat tomonidan tartibga solishda marketing yondashuvi.....	65
Amonov Mehridin Oromiddinovich	
Infratuzilmani rivojlantirish – mintaqalar raqobatbardoshligini oshirish drayveri sifatida	70
Sayfulina Alfira Feratovna	
Soliq nazorati jamoatchilik nazoratining shakli sifatida.....	79
Suvonov Hasan Sherboyevich	
Разработка интеллектуальной системы управления многостадийными технологическими процессами.....	84
Алишев Шеркузи Абдуманнонович	
Masofaviy xodimlarning mehnat faoliyatini rag'batlantirish tizimini rivojlantirish	91
Tolliboyev Samad Tolliboy o'g'li	
Sug'urta xizmatlari bozorida raqobatbardoshlikni oshirish yo'llari	99
Umirov Abdusalom To'rayevich	
IoT tarmoqlari uchun optimallashtirish usullarini tahlil qilish	105
Abdug'aniyev Bekzod Burxon o'g'li	
Tarmoq xavfsizligini ta'minlashda zamonaviy texnologiyalar va usullar	110
Raxmonkulov Feruz Pardaboyevich	
Qishloq xo'jaligi tarmog'ida innovatsion jarayonlarni moliyalashtirish holatining matematik modeli.....	114
Ishniyazov Baxrom Normamatovich	
Sug'urtada anderrayting xizmatini raqamlashtirish orqali sug'urta mukofoti va to'lovlarni amalga oshirishni takomillashtirish	120
Mirzoyev Sayfullo Fayzulloevich	
Korxonalar faoliyatini yashil obligatsiyalar orqali moliyalashtirish imkoniyatlari.....	128
Muxiddin Eshmuradov	
Aholi turmush farovonligini oshirishning inson omiliga ta'siri.....	133
Sharofiddin Ismatov Asatulloevich	
Soliq salohiyatini baholashning zamonaviy metodlari va ularning rivojlantirish istiqbollari	137
Jo'rayev Xusan Atamuratovich	

Ish o'rinlarini qonuniylashtirish orqali yashirin iqtisodiyotni qisqartirish yo'llari.....	143
Dilshod To'rayev	
Davlat tashkilotlarida g'aznachilik va davlat xaridlari bilan bog'liq jarayon holatining tahlili.....	147
Mamasoliyev Abrorbek Abdug'ani o'g'li	
Iqtisodiy transformatsiyalashuv sharoitida aholi bandligini ta'minlashning ayrim masalalari.....	152
Salomat Norova	
Moliyaviy sektorni soliqqa tortish.....	159
Komolov Odiljon Sayfidinovich	
Bojxona ma'muriyatchiligini takomillashtirishda bojxona menejmentini shakllantirish metodikasi.....	165
Mirzaxmedova Dilafruz Farxatovna, Tuxbabayev Jamshid Sharafetdinovich	
O'zbekiston tijorat banklari tomonidan kreditlash amaliyotini rivojlantirish istiqbollari.....	171
Kaxxarov Ulug'bek Xalmatovich	
Mamlakatda moliyaviy xavfsizlikni ta'minlashning nazariy jihatlari.....	177
Azamatov Po'lat To'lqunovich	
Surxondaryo viloyati tumanlari iqtisodiyotidagi tarkibiy jarayonlarning o'ziga xos xususiyatlari.....	183
Normurodov Alibek Anvar o'g'li	
Raqamli iqtisodiyotni shakllantirish sharoitida yoqilg'i-energetika kompleksi korxonalarini barqaror innovatsion rivojlantirish modellari.....	189
Bobobekov Ergash Abdumalikovich	
Asosiy vositalarni audit obyekti sifatida tasnifi va tavsifi.....	196
Ibragimov Mansur Mardonovich, Orzumurodova Farangiz Damirovna	
Iqtisodiyot taraqqiyotini soliqlar orqali tartibga solish va rag'batlantirishga kreativ yondashuvning samarali tadbirlari.....	201
Rajabbaeva Dildora Zakirovna	
Роль цифровизации в обеспечении экономической безопасности предприятий.....	206
Махмудова Гулжахон Нематджоновна, Жанызакова Шахноза Мажит кизи	
Transport korxonalarida xarajatlar va daromadlar hisobini takomillashtirish masalalari.....	215
Jabbarov Umarbek Rustambekovich, Rustamova Dilnura Umarovna	
To'qimachilik klasterlarining eksport salohiyatini baholash asosida iqtisodiy xavfsizligini ta'minlash masalalari.....	220
Sadriddinova Nigora Khusniddinovna	
Uzum yetishtiruvchi fermer xo'jaliklari faoliyatida innovatsiyalardan foydalanish darajasini baholash.....	227
Boltayev Nazarbek Narzullayevich	
Совершенствование управленческого учета в узбекистане: проблемы, интеграция и перспективы развития.....	236
Киличева Ф.Б.	
Tijorat banklari tomonidan masofaviy xizmat turlarini rivojlantirish yo'llari.....	241
Muxitdinov Ulugbek Diyarovich	
Tijorat banklari tomonidan investitsion kreditlarni rivojlantirishning xorijiy davlatlar tajribalari.....	246
Zaynutdinov Bunyodjon Odiljon o'g'li	
Korxonalarni inqirozga yetaklovchi omillar va ularni oldini olishga qaratilgan chora tadbirlar.....	255
Muxammadov Umarjon Muxammad o'g'li	
Kasalliklarni erta aniqlash imkoniyatlarini oshirishda zamonaviy dasturiy ta'minotning roli.....	260
Mamatov Maxtumquli Jumanazarovich	

Qoyali zaminlarda gravitatsion to'g'onlar tasnifi	264
Maksimov Dilmurodbek Erkinjonovich	
Improvement of financing the innovation projects of business entities.....	270
Jubanova Bayramgul Aymuratovna	

MUNDARIJA СОДЕРЖАНИЕ CONTENTS

IMPROVEMENT OF FINANCING THE INNOVATION PROJECTS OF BUSINESS ENTITIES

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Annotatsiya: In this article, the financing of innovative projects of business entities is analyzed from a scientific and theoretical point of view, the current state of financing of innovative projects of business entities in our country, especially organizational innovations of small and private business entities, is analyzed, and scientific and practical recommendations are developed.

Kalit so'zlar: business entities, small and private business entities, innovative projects, financing, organizational innovations, credit.

Abstract: Ushbu maqolada tadbirkorlik subyektlarining innovatsion loyihalarini moliyalashtirish ilmiy-nazariy jihatdan tahlil qilingan, mamlakatimizda tadbirkorlik subyektlarining innovatsion loyihalari, xususan, kichik va xususiy tadbirkorlik subyektlarining tashkiliy innovatsiyalarini moliyalashtirishning amaldagi holati tahlil qilingan hamda ilmiy-amaliy tavsiyalar ishlab chiqilgan.

Keywords: tadbirkorlik subyektlari, kichik tadbirkorlik subyektlari, innovatsion loyihalar, moliyalashtirish, tashkiliy innovatsiyalar, kredit.

Аннотация: В данной статье научно-теоретически исследуется финансирование инновационных проектов субъектов предпринимательства, анализируется современное состояние финансирования инновационных проектов субъектов предпринимательства, особенности организационных инноваций субъектов малого и частного предпринимательства в нашей стране, и разработаны научно-практические рекомендации.

Ключевые слова: субъекты малого предпринимательства, инновационные проекты, финансирование, организационные инновации, кредит.

INTRODUCTION

The role of business entities in the economy of our country is growing, and according to the results of 2023, their share in the country's gross domestic product was 51.2 percent, in industry - 26.9 percent, in agriculture - 94.8 percent, in investments - 51.4 percent, in construction - 74.7 percent, in retail trade - 83.8 percent, in services - 47.7 percent, in freight transportation - 50.8 percent, in passenger transportation - 91.6 percent, in exports - 29.0 percent, and in imports - 50.7 percent¹. As can be seen from this data, one of the priority tasks facing the government of the country is to create more favorable conditions for the development of business entities, which play an extremely important role in the country's economy, and financing their innovative projects is of particular importance in this regard.

The digital economy, characterized by sharp changes in the competitive environment, requires business entities to work on innovative projects. The implementation of such projects requires

¹ Newsletter of the Statistics Agency under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan: small business. 15.02.2024. Pages 232-257. www.stat.uz

financing, and in this article we will consider the issues of financing innovative projects of business entities.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE ON THE SUBJECT

Financing innovative projects of business entities is one of the problems being studied by foreign and domestic scientists and researchers, and below we will briefly analyze the approaches and views on this issue. In addition, we will give an example from the experience of CIS countries in this regard.

A group of foreign scientists and researchers - Anabela M. Santos from Spain, Michele Cincera from Belgium and Giovanni Cerulli from Italy - in their scientific research, they discussed eight sources of financing for innovative projects of business entities, including internal funds, bank loans, credit lines, trade credit, private equity, grants or subsidies, leasing and factoring. According to scientists and researchers, not all of these sources of financing have the same impact on the development of innovative projects. However, if all of them are used together, this will allow not only the development of innovative activities of business entities, but also their comprehensive growth².

Table 1 below presents these funding sources and their level of impact on the development of innovative projects.

In order to finance innovative projects of business entities in the Russian Federation, a federal project called "Flight - from startup to IPO" is being implemented, and within the framework of this project, the Innovation Support Fund, in cooperation with the Ministry of Economic Development, regularly holds a competition called "Business - Start". This competition aims to select innovative projects that involve the creation, expansion and (or) modernization of production necessary for the serial production and commercialization of an innovative product (table 1).

Table 1. Sources of financing for innovative projects of business entities³.

#	Sources	Description	Level of impact on innovation activity
1.	Internal funds	Cash or cash equivalents arising from savings, retained earnings, or the sale of assets	Medium
2.	Bank loans	Long-term debt and financing cost (interest rate)	Low
3.	Credit lines	Short-term loans that can be used in whole or in part at will, within a predetermined limit	Low
4.	Trade credit	Making payments to suppliers of goods, services, or equipment at a later, mutually agreed upon time	Low
5.	Private equity	Proceeds from the sale of a business entity's share	Medium
6.	Grants or subsidies	Non-repayable funds, low-interest or interest-free loans provided by the government	High
7.	Leasing	Making regular payments for the use of a fixed asset without direct ownership	Low
8.	Factoring	Selling customer debts to a factoring company for immediate cash, but at a price lower than their value	Medium

According to the Deputy Minister of Economic Development of Russia, Maxim Kolesnikov, within the framework of the federal project "Flight - from startup to IPO", startups are supported by the

² Anabela M. Santos, Michele Cincera and Giovanni Cerulli. Sources of financing: Which ones are more effective in innovation-growth linkage? // Economic Systems. Volume 48, Issue 2, June 2024. 15 pages.

³ Source: Anabela M. Santos, Michele Cincera and Giovanni Cerulli. Sources of financing: Which ones are more effective in innovation-growth linkage? // Economic Systems. Volume 48, Issue 2, June 2024. 15 pages.

state at each stage of their development, from the expansion of their activities to improving the product based on the requirements of large customers and entering the stock market. One of the most important tools for supporting product improvement and increasing the scale of production is grants. According to the results of this year's "Business Start" competition, 33 small businesses received financial support totaling 372 million rubles, and their innovative projects include 3D printing, biometrics and information security systems, the creation of medical devices, as well as the development of new devices for various industries and agriculture.

The Deputy Minister added that priority is given to business entities with the status of small technology companies in the competition: additional points are awarded when considering and evaluating their innovation projects. Therefore, every second winner of the competition is a business entity with the status of a small technology company.

Sergey Polyakov, Director General of the Innovation Support Fund, noted that the provision of grants of up to 12 million rubles to each of the competition winners will allow them to direct the funds to marketing services and industrial design, as well as the purchase of equipment, components and software, that is, to carry out all the work necessary to launch a new or improved product on the market⁴.

Local researcher Atamuradov Sh. A. studied the place and role of venture capital in financing innovative projects of business entities, and he said that in international experience, venture capital greatly helps in financing practical ideas. The results of studying the experience of countries such as the USA, Japan, Singapore, Finland and India show that financing through venture capital can radically change the quality of the innovative model of economic development, provide it with investment, ultimately lead to economic growth and eliminate the investment deficit. Atamuradov Sh. A. added that in this case, innovative projects of business entities are financed through private investments. The goal of directing these investments is to receive a profit in the future if the innovative project is successful. Venture financing is unique in that it is characterized by high risk and long-term (from three to seven years)⁵.

In general, an analysis of the literature on the financing of innovative projects of business entities shows that the role of the state in this area is very large, and its support, mainly through grants or subsidies, provides an important impetus for the development of innovative projects.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This article was prepared in accordance with the requirements of the international IMRAD structure, and three main research methods were used: the scientific-theoretical analysis method, the theoretical-practical analysis method, and the economic-statistical analysis method. The scientific-theoretical analysis method was used mainly to analyze the data collected for the "Literature Review" section of the article, while the economic-statistical analysis method was used to analyze the data collected for the "Analysis and Results" section of the article. The theoretical-practical analysis method was used in both of these sections of the article.

In the process of collecting data for the "Literature Review", Google, Google Scholar and Yandex search engines, as well as the Elsevier international scientific journal database, were mainly used. The main focus was on studying online and printed literature from 2019 to the present, and mainly English-language literature was used to study the scientific and theoretical views of foreign scientists and researchers on the topic, mainly Russian-language literature was used to analyze the theoretical and practical experience of the CIS countries, and mainly Uzbek and Russian-language literature was used to study the opinions of local scientists and researchers.

In the process of collecting data for the "Analysis and Results", primary and secondary research sources were mainly used. When using primary research sources, interviews were organized with local scientists, researchers, and experts related to the field of financing innovative projects

4 Малые технологические компании из 20 регионов получили гранты на инновационные проекты. 08.08.2024. Официальный вебсайт Фонда содействия инновациям. www.fasie.ru

5 Atamuradov Sh. A. Innovatsion faoliyatni venchurli moliyalashtirishning xalqaro modellarini joriy etish samaradorligi // Iqtisod va moliya / Экономика и финансы 2019, 1(121). 47-55-betlar.

of business entities, while when using secondary research sources, Google and Yandex search engines, local news websites, and reports and statistical bulletins of relevant organizations were consulted.

In general, in preparing the article, an effort was made to make maximum use of information and data, adhere to logical sequence and coherence, and avoid the “copy-paste” method, which can lead to plagiarism. This helped to achieve the main goal of the study - the development of scientific and practical recommendations on improvement of the financing the innovative projects of business entities.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

As in other countries of the world, attention is being paid to the financing of innovative projects of business entities in our country, and the main goal is to increase the production of import-substituting and export-oriented products in the country, increase employment and income sources, develop national brands that can compete in the world market, as well as achieve the formation of digital, green and sustainable economies. Indeed, in achieving these goals, business entities, together with their innovative projects, play the role of a “driver”. In this part of our article, we will consider the current state of financing the innovative projects of business entities in the country based on analytical data. We would like to draw your attention to Table 2. This table shows the number of innovations introduced by small and private businesses in Uzbekistan over the past three years (table 2).

Table 2. The number of innovations introduced by small and private businesses in Uzbekistan in 2021-2023⁶.

#	Types of innovations	2021	2022	2023
1.	Technological innovations	2778	1541	1815
2.	Marketing innovations	129	40	45
3.	Organizational innovations	33	54	278
Total:		2940	1635	2138

Before analyzing the data presented in Table 2, we ask you to pay attention to Figure 1 below, which provides a brief overview of the types of innovations - technological innovations, marketing innovations, and organizational innovations (figure 1).

Figure 1. Types of Innovations⁷

6 Sources: Activities of small enterprises and microfirms in the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2021. State Statistics Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Tashkent-2022, 45 pages; Activity of small enterprises and micro-firms in the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2022. Statistics Agency under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Tashkent-2023, 36 pages.; Main indicators of the activity of small enterprises and micro-firms in the Republic of Uzbekistan (for 2023). Statistics Agency under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Tashkent-2024, 31 pages.

7 Source: Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On Innovative Activities”. July 24, 2020, No. 630.

Now, returning to the analysis of the data in Table 2, the amount of innovations introduced by small and private businesses in 2022, especially technological innovations and marketing innovations, decreased sharply compared to 2021, and continued to grow again in 2023. However, the amount of organizational innovations continued to grow steadily, even showing a very high result by 2023. If we pay attention to the description of organizational innovations in Figure 1, we can get an idea of the following two main reasons for such growth:

Firstly, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. DP-93 dated June 12, 2023 “On measures aimed at establishing mutually beneficial cooperation with business entities in poverty reduction” provided for business entities that create from 51 to 200 new jobs and more, providing benefits and preferences in areas such as “financing”, “taxation”, “providing necessary funds and infrastructure for the activities of business entities”, “simplification of tax and customs administration”, and “strengthening legal protection of business entities” further accelerated the pace of implementation of organizational innovations⁸. Indeed, the description of organizational innovation in Figure 1 includes a sentence that reads «innovations aimed at introducing new or improved methods of organizing jobs,» and the tasks set out in this Decree of our President correspond to the description of organizational innovation.

According to this Decree, such business entities are included in the program “20 thousand entrepreneurs - 500 thousand qualified specialists” and are provided with differentiated benefits and preferences in the areas mentioned above. Since the issue under consideration is related to financing, in Figure 2 below we present information on the benefits and preferences provided only in the area of financing (figure 2):

Figure 2. Maximum amounts of loans allocated for the implementation of projects of business entities for a period of up to 7 years at a rate of 14%, billion soums⁹.

As can be seen from Figure 2, the Decree of the President No. DP-93 dated June 12, 2023 established the allocation of loans for business entities that create from 51 to 100 new jobs - 5 billion soums, for business entities that create from 101 to 200 new jobs - 10 billion soums, and for business entities that create more than 200 new jobs - 15 billion soums for a period of up to 7 years at a rate of 14%. This undoubtedly allowed for a sharp increase in the amount of organizational innovations introduced by small businesses and private entrepreneurs in 2023.

8 Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On measures aimed at establishing mutually beneficial cooperation with business entities in poverty reduction”. June 12, 2023, No. DP-93.

9 Source: Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On measures aimed at establishing mutually beneficial cooperation with business entities in poverty reduction”. June 12, 2023, No. DP-93.

Secondly, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. DP-228 dated September 30, 2022 “On measures to further expand the export potential of business entities” began to allocate financial resources to business entities based on the volume of exports carried out over the last 12 months to finance pre-export and export-related trade operations at the expense of the Export Support Fund, which also served as an important impetus for increasing the number of organizational innovations ¹⁰.

If we pay attention to the description of organizational innovations in Figure 1, there is a sentence that says «innovations aimed at introducing new or improved methods of establishing external relations», which means that the financing the export activities of business entities, in essence, reflects the financing the organizational innovations.

Figure 3 below presents information on financing the export activities of business entities, as established by the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. DP-228 of September 30, 2022 (figure 3):

Figure 3. Financial resources allocated from the Export Support Fund based on the export volume of business entities, million dollars ¹¹.

As can be seen from Figure 3, if the export volume of a business entity in the last 12 months is from \$1 million to \$5 million - up to \$1 million, from \$5 million to \$10 million - up to \$2 million, from \$10 million to \$15 million - up to \$3 million, from \$15 million to \$20 million - up to \$4 million, and from \$20 million to more than \$5 million - financial resources will be allocated from the Export Support Fund. In addition, if business entities that meet these requirements implement one international standard and receive a certificate, they will be provided with financial assistance in the amount of no more than \$30,000¹².

From this, we can conclude that the support of the export activities of business entities by the Decree of the President No. DP-228 has made it possible to observe a steady, and even sharp, growth trend in the number of organizational innovations introduced by them by 2023.

¹⁰ Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On measures to further expand the export potential of business entities”, September 30, 2022, No. DP-228.

¹¹ Source: Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On measures to further expand the export potential of business entities”, September 30, 2022, No. DP-228.

¹² Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On measures to further expand the export potential of business entities”, September 30, 2022, No. DP-228.

In general, as mentioned above, in addition to organizational innovations of small and private businesses, there are also technological and marketing innovations, which we will try to cover in our further research. However, we can say with certainty that the main reason for the growth trend in these types of innovations in 2023 can be traced back to the reforms implemented by the state to finance them (such as organizational innovations). Because the role of the state in financing innovative projects of business entities in our country is extremely important.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

In conclusion, in our country, significant attention is paid to financing innovative projects of business entities, as can be seen from the above analytical data and the reviewed regulatory and legal documents. At this point, we would like to reiterate that the state is the main force in financing innovative projects of business entities. Based on this, we would like to present our scientific and practical recommendations below:

it is necessary to further increase the sources of financing for innovative projects of business entities: as can be seen from the above analysis, in our country, such sources of financing consist mainly of loans provided by commercial banks (mostly banks with state shares) and subsidies provided by various state funds, in addition, it would be advisable to fully utilize leasing, factoring, credit lines, trade credit, private equity, internal funds, grants and other similar sources. The more sources of financing are used, the more business entities will have the opportunity to develop and implement innovative projects;

it is necessary to increase the number of competitions for the allocation of grants for financing innovative projects of business entities: there are not enough such competitions in our country, which can also lead to a decrease in the interest of entrepreneurs in implementing innovations. During the research, we only received information about the competition for startup projects, which is being implemented in cooperation with the Agency for Innovation Development under the Ministry of Higher Education, Science and Innovation of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the Russian Federation. We believe that the holding of more and more such competitions will lead to the further development of innovative activities of business entities;

It is necessary to improve the statistics on startups, which occupy an important place in the topic of «innovative projects of business entities»: due to the inaccuracy of such statistics during the study, we decided to leave our research on it for further research. It is precisely the poor statistics that may hinder the attraction of international venture investors who want to invest in startups. We believe that it is time to create a website in our country that would contain all the most complete statistical information about startups, etc.

In general, a lot of positive and significant work is being done in our country to finance innovative projects of business entities, which in the future will lead to the formation of a class of successful entrepreneurs not only at the national level, but also at the international level. We hope that the scientific and practical recommendations developed as a result of our research will make a worthy contribution to this.

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